

China's Miracle of Poverty Eradication: A Model of State-Led Development and Human Rights Protection

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Great achievements have been made in the fight against poverty since Chinese President Xi Jinping took office in 2012. Since the 18th National Congress of the Communist Party of China (CPC) at the end of 2012, a new era aimed at reducing poverty has been launched.

Figure 1. Number of people living in extreme poverty in China (2012–2020).

Source: (Statista.com, 2020)

As Figure-1 above clearly shows, China has lifted nearly 100 million people out of poverty between 2012 and 2020. This means fulfilling the poverty eradication program set out in the United Nations' 2030 Sustainable Development Program 10 years ahead of schedule. Under the leadership of President Xi Jinping and the CPC, China is moving step by step closer to the goal of eradicating extreme poverty and building a moderately prosperous society.

In the last 40 years, China has lifted more than 800 million people out of poverty, realizing a miracle in human history and becoming the country that has made the greatest contribution to the fight against poverty in the international arena.

China's success in reducing poverty has also been a concrete manifestation of its practical achievements in fulfilling the most basic state duties such as protecting and promoting human rights, providing housing and employment.

Poverty alleviation in China has been given special attention from the top leadership to the lowest organs of the state. This was clearly demonstrated by Chinese President Xi's on-site inspection of poverty eradication work in his home province of Shaanxi from 20 to 24 April 2020. Xi Jinping inspects an organic yellow lily farm in Yunzhu county, Datong city! He visited the homes of poor farmers and shared a meal with them. Through the yellow lily trade, this town has eradicated extreme poverty. Immediately after Xi's visit, demand for Yunzhu's lilies soared. (*Xinhua*, 2020)

China's fight against poverty is not a "zero-sum game". China is also making important contributions to the fight against poverty outside China. For example, it has helped to build 24 agricultural technology demonstration centers in Africa, creating employment for more than 500,000 people. According to data from the World Bank, the Belt and Road Initiative is expected to lift 7.6 million people out of extreme poverty and 32 million out of moderate poverty. Over the past four decades, China's fight against poverty has contributed over 70 percent to poverty reduction efforts worldwide, according to official figures (Omoruyi, 2019).

Let us quote this success in the World Bank's own words: "China's success in reducing poverty over the past 25 years is enviable. With 1.3 billion inhabitants, it is impossible not to be impressed by what this populous nation has achieved in such a short time. In terms of a wide range of indicators, the progress and achievements are striking. Incomes and consumption have risen and poverty has fallen dramatically. Progress also applies to the human development index: most of the 'Millennium Development Goals' have already been achieved or are close to being achieved. Although there is no official urban poverty line, estimates have found that the level of poverty in urban areas is negligible. These estimates therefore suggest that only 1 percent of the Chinese population is currently in extreme poverty." (World Bank, 2009)

Xi reveals the secret of success

On 16 April 2019, Xi Jinping chaired a well-attended meeting in Chongqing entitled "Solving Major Problems in Fighting Poverty". The Chinese President's speech at this meeting was published in the December 2019 issue of *QiuShi*, the theoretical organ of the Communist Party of China. President Xi describes how China has succeeded in overcoming poverty: "First, we have steadily promoted poverty eradication. The number of rural residents living below the poverty line fell from 98 million 990 thousand people in 2012 to 16 million 600 thousand people in 2018. We have lifted 82 million 390 thousand people out of absolute poverty. On average, more than ten million people have been lifted out of poverty every year for six years. And the poverty rate in China fell from 10.2 percent to 1.7 percent.

"After adopting the new standards to eliminate poverty, we stopped calculating the struggle targets on the basis of two-year periods and moved them to an annual basis. We demolished the delusion that a bottleneck would be reached after reducing the poor population to 30 million and that it would be impossible to go below this figure. Despite our efforts to reduce poverty on a population basis, the number of poor districts, which had been increasing, is now decreasing. After fulfilling the task of lifting 10 million people and 330 districts out of poverty in 2019, it is estimated that by the beginning of 2020 there will be only six million poor and around 60 poor districts across the country.

"Second, we have ensured that all our poor citizens have enough food and clothing, and we have ensured that people in most areas have access to roads, drinking water, electricity, communications, education, medical services and safe housing.

"Third, construction work in relocating poor villages to nearby areas is nearing completion. During the 13th Five-Year Plan period (2016-2020), it is planned to relocate about 10 million citizens in absolute poverty from uninhabitable areas. By the end of last year, construction work on the relocation of 8.7 million people had been completed and most of the relocated people had been lifted out of poverty. We expect the remaining construction work to be fully completed this year.

"Fourth, the CPC's management units in rural areas have been further consolidated. The erroneous approaches of a large number of officials in fighting poverty have been corrected, the effectiveness of local CPC organisations in rural areas has been significantly upgraded, their dedication to the cause has been strengthened, rural governance ability at the local level has been improved, and management capacity has been significantly enhanced. We have made great progress in improving the relationship between the CPC and the people, as well as between the leaders and the people." (*qstheory*, 2021)

China's Development Strategy

The main feature of the Chinese economic development model is that the market is "driven" by a strong government and the state sector guides the national economy (Jinglian & Shitao, 2014). State guidance for the economy has allowed China to accumulate large amounts of capital and strategically mobilize this accumulated wealth to be used to support the expansion of a productive economy (Yongding, 2014).

China sees science and technology as an integral pillar of its economic development. This is the main reason why China's industrial strategies also reflect a science and technology-oriented approach. Made in China 2025, China's national strategic plan for industrial policy as part of "Industry 4.0", is a case in point. It was launched in 2015. This plan calls for the integration of new technologies into the economy and the development of a national industrial base led by domestic innovation. It provides an overall framework for mobilizing state support for key industries such as information, technology, robotics, green energy, sustainable transport, aerospace technology, ocean engineering and high-tech ships,

railway equipment, new materials and pioneering medical and agricultural technologies. High-tech companies operating in these sectors will be supported through tax incentives, subsidies, low-interest loans, R&D financing and assistance for the acquisition of foreign technology companies.

Conclusion

Before the democratic people's revolution led by the Chinese Communist Party (CPC) in 1949, China was among the poorest countries in the world. Under the "medieval" conditions imposed by an agrarian economy and a weak industrial infrastructure, it was struggling with the paralyzing effects of its semi-colonial legacy. Historical circumstances aside, China has a very large population, 22 percent of the total world population. China has a large population. Despite its large population size, China's natural resource scarcity has been a major obstacle to its development potential. China has only 7 percent of the world's arable land and freshwater resources and only 8 percent of the world's natural resources. 65 percent of its surface area is too hilly for agriculture and only 19 percent is suitable for human habitation.

Another factor undermining China's development potential is related to geopolitical challenges. Simply put, China was blocked from joining the United Nations (UN) until 1971. In order to stifle the Chinese revolution, the United States and its allies have been using the geopolitical interventions in countries. Today, these challenges find their sharpest expression in the trade and technology war waged by the US against China as part of its containment policy (Gürcan, 2019).

Despite all these challenging conditions, China has demonstrated an unprecedented economic development performance and provided an exemplary model to the developing world. Since 1979, it is the only economy in the world that has never experienced an economic crisis. During the 1979-2018 period, China's economy grew at an average annual rate of 9.4 percent under CPC rule and became the second largest economy in the world. Thus, it has established itself as the world's largest producer and exporter. In the last months of 2020, with the elimination of extreme poverty, the great development breakthrough, which is called the "Chinese miracle" today, has added a new one to its success.

In 1950, China, which was even more backward in terms of development than any African country, has today become a country that has ended extreme poverty, a pioneer in space studies, and a country where advanced studies are carried out in terms of artificial intelligence and integrated systems. The main reasons for these achievements can be listed as follows:

- The realization of an independent economy geared towards promoting national sovereignty and limiting the effects of foreign interference
- Maintaining the socialist system and relying on the leadership of a party capable of strategic coherence and long-term planning
- Building a strong industrial infrastructure fueled by national science and technology policies

and shaped by public leadership

- To put into effect a balanced development approach that seeks to achieve a higher standard of living in socio-cultural and ecological terms.

Certainly, the great sacrifices of the Chinese people under the leadership of the CPC are one of the main reasons for China's development success. The economic success of the West owes more to the forced accumulation of capital through colonialism and slavery than to the miracle of free markets (Wallerstein, 2015). Unlike Western capitalism, China's economic miracle has nothing to do with forced accumulation, wars, colonialism and slavery. Rather, the Chinese miracle is the result of peaceful development and international co-operation. In fact, it can be safely said that the mode followed by China demonstrates the growing relevance of the socialist system and constitutes the most vivid example of its superiority over Western capitalism.

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